

**ON THE ISSUE OF THE ORGANIZATION OF RESEARCH
ACTIVITIES OF UNDERGRADUATES IN THE PROCESS OF
TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN UNIVERSITIES OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.**

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Annotation. The article discusses the organization of research activities of undergraduates in the process of teaching the Russian language in a state university. Research activity is an important criterion for the success of the professional activity of a future specialist. The article emphasizes the need for active research work in the process of teaching the Russian language in the magistracy.

Key words: research activity, research assignments, project assignments, undergraduates, Russian language, state university.

In the process of training undergraduates at the university, special attention is paid to research activities, which are one of the most important components of the professional competence of a future specialist. The need to conduct research activities in the master's degree is due to the nature of professional activity. Conducting active research work in the process of studying for a master's degree contributes to the creation of an environment for the formation of scientific creativity, the possibility of scientific interest, the development of research competence [1, 51].

The purpose of the article is to consider the organization of research activities of undergraduates in the process of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university. Research activity, according to I.A. Zimnaya, acts as "the ability to conduct independent observations, experiments acquired in the process of solving various kinds of research tasks" [3, 56].

The pedagogical system of management of students' research activities in the process of learning the Russian language is defined as "professional pedagogical

activity representing the organization of foreign language activities of students, the formation of competence for independent search, systematization, analysis of foreign language information, the realization of internal potential" [1, 22]. Research activity includes the ability to work with scientific literature, search, evaluate and store scientific data, critically evaluate the information received, the ability to formulate problems and scientific hypotheses, to argue their position [1, 56]. The Master's degree program teaches certain "research actions" [4, 16] to generalize, synthesize, analyze, evaluate, etc. In the process of teaching a foreign language in the magistracy, a foreign language environment and effective conditions for creating a research process and professional interaction are formed [2, 75]. In this regard, topical issues on the organization of research activities of undergraduates are outlined.

In the process of teaching the Russian language in the master's program, a foreign language environment and effective conditions for creating a research process and professional interaction are formed [1, 21]. In this regard, topical issues on the organization of research activities of undergraduates are outlined. The curricula of the discipline "Russian Language" provide for mastering the skills of annotation, developing the skill of reviewing literature for academic purposes: extracting information, processing it, summarizing the content of articles read and their critical evaluation, compiling a glossary.

In the Russian language classes, the teacher determines the types of activities and exercises that ensure that the classes are filled with research, project and creative forms of work. Students of the Master's degree may be offered project research tasks that provide for obtaining a scientific or applied scientific product as a result - making a report at a scientific conference, making a presentation, writing an abstract, articles on the research topic under study and publishing them in scientific journals, preparing for a scientific discussion, creating oral reports, participating in round tables tables, etc.

Thus, research activity is an essential condition for the preparation of graduate students. [4, 29]. Scientific research activities organized, including by means of the Russian language, are an important criterion for the success of the professional activity of a future specialist. Russian language classes are filled with research and project activities and exercises that contribute to the development of research skills and scientific creativity skills of students.

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